

Biomedical Education: A Simple Guide for Histological Reporting

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Abstract

Basic and accurate histological examination of hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stained slides is a critical skill for biomedical researchers. However, many postgraduate students struggle to interpret these slides, relying on external assistance for histological reporting. This knowledge gap can have long-term implications for research validity and career advancement. This paper presents a concise and structured approach to documenting H&E-stained histology slides, outlining essential assessment criteria and addressing common challenges. Emphasizing the importance of practice and experience in achieving proficiency, this framework aims to enhance research competency in biomedicine and promote accurate histological reporting.

Keywords: Histology, H&E staining, Slide reporting

Introduction

It is not unusual to get a good number of students submitting the histological slides of their Bachelor's or Master's research projects to be primarily read or interpreted by someone else, but this is a misnomer. Especially for students with backgrounds in histology. They should be capable of interpreting and generating fundamental histological information from their slides. Histological evaluation of hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stained sections (slides) is a valuable skill in research and disease diagnosis [1]. However, the ability of the biologist to read H&E-stained slides requires some knowledge of the stains, the cytoarchitecture, and cellular morphology of the structure or organ of interest [1, 2]. It is stated in textbooks and online resources that H& E is routine for diagnosis, and is by far preferred for viewing cellular and

tissue structure details by pathologists. This has created a mindset in most life sciences researchers that only a pathologist can obtain information from their research slides. H& E is not only basic for clinical investigation, but is almost exclusively used in basic research [3].

Researchers with a background in histology should be proficient in independently examining and interpreting their histology slides. While collaborative study is essential for validating findings and ensuring high-quality research, histology-trained researchers should possess the fundamental skills to extract fundamental or simple information from their project slides. This competency is crucial for maintaining research autonomy, ensuring data accuracy, and fostering effective collaboration. They are not expected to define any pathological disease. This educational resource aims to provide a concise and accessible guide for students, outlining a straightforward approach to reporting and evaluating H&E-stained histological slides. Clear, step-by-step instructions and practical tips facilitate confident and accurate histological assessment.

Prerequisite Knowledge

First and foremost, the students must be familiar with the basics of the normal histology of the tissue or organ of interest. Secondly, the student must recall that hematoxylin stains acidic structures, such as nuclei, blue/purple, and eosin stains basic structures, such as cytoplasm, pink/red [4]. Other acidic structures are ribosomes and rough endoplasmic reticulum. Other basic structures include collagen and extracellular matrix. Furthermore, intracellular components like lipids and water do not react with the hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stain and remain unstained.

Reading H&E Slides

Start with the Fundamentals

(a) Begin by examining the tissue section at low and medium magnifications to identify the overall tissue structure and cell type, noting any deviations from normal architecture ($\times 4$ and $\times 10$).

(b) Then search for and describe the following: not all may be present.

- i. Nuclei: Identify the blue/purple-stained nuclei, the round or oval structures within the cells.
- ii. Cytoplasm: Identify the pink/red-stained cytoplasm, the material surrounding the nucleus within the cell.

- iii. Extracellular Matrix: Note the pink/red staining of the extracellular matrix, material between cells, such as in collagen fibers.
- iv. Other Structures: Note that other structures, red blood cells, for example, can be stained by eosin and be pink/red as well.
- v. Air Spaces: Air spaces will be colorless or white.
- vi. Stain Intensity: Intensity of staining can vary depending on the type of tissue and the staining technique.
- vii. Artifacts: Be aware of potential artifacts, like air bubbles or crystals, which may resemble or mask tissue structures.
- viii. "Bluing" Step: The "bluing" step, during which hematoxylin stain is placed under an alkaline material, is important for achieving proper blue/purple nuclei coloration [2].

Shift Focus to Details

Once having some idea of the overall form, examine the details at medium and high power for the shape of the cell, nucleus, or tissue organization. Note any distinctive or unusual features observed in the tissue sample. Subsequently, conduct a comparative analysis with the established normal histological architecture for that specific tissue type, highlighting any deviations or discrepancies that may indicate pathology or abnormality.

Use Multiple Magnifications

A thorough examination of tissue samples involves a multi-magnification approach, commencing with low-power magnification (40x-100x) to obtain a comprehensive overview, followed by high-power magnification (200x-400x) to scrutinize cellular details and detect subtle alterations. Throughout the examination, precise adjustments to focus and lighting are essential to optimize image clarity.

Hindrance to Proper H& E Interpretation

Poor staining or fixation can result from substandard or low-quality tissue processing reagents or chemicals. Variation in staining intensity should be expected because there is great variation in the proportion of parenchyma and stroma between organs [5, 6]. Stain intensity can also vary with the type of tissue and staining procedure [2, 6]. Thus, your knowledge of the normal histology is crucial in making a sound interpretation. Thus, good grips of your histological technique are crucial [2, 4].

Using the Microscope

While stressed earlier, but stressed again for importance, when examining H&E stained histological sections under the microscope: (a), start with low power (40x-100x) for a "gross" appearance of the tissue architecture; (b) use high power (200x-400x) to evaluate cellular alterations, e.g., swelling and shrinkage of cells, swelling, condensation, or fragmentation of nuclei; (c), alternate focus and illumination.

Simple Illustrations

In these illustrations, our focus is on basic histological concepts learned during undergraduate training, without describing any pathological conditions, which is usually sufficient for our purposes in many instances.

1. Liver Sections

Histological section of normal liver (A) showing hepatocytes radiating from the central (v), and sinusoidal spaces. Fig. 1 B is a section from another liver; note that all the features seen in the normal liver (A) were absent. Hence, it can be reported as: a section of liver (B) shows abnormal cytoarchitectural features, hepatocytes seem depleted with infiltration of fat cells. Sinusoidal spaces were occluded or obliterated. **CC BY-NC**

2. Lung Sections

Histological section of normal lung(A) showing numerous alveolar sacs. The section in B shows occluded or degenerating alveolar sacs. **CC BY-NC**

Discussion and Conclusion

The widespread adoption of H&E staining in examining biological samples can be attributed to its simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and ability to elucidate intricate microscopic details. Additionally, it serves as a valuable tool in the diagnosis of numerous histopathological conditions. The fixative used or modifications made by individual laboratories do not heavily influence the results from H&E staining [7, 8], making it the most widely used method in histology. Following the outlined steps enables a diligent student to develop a high level of comfort and proficiency in interpreting their histology slides. This newfound expertise will, in turn, greatly bolster their confidence when defending their research projects, ultimately leading to a more successful and convincing presentation. The students must also remember that reading slides is not a smooth process. Your reading is knowledge-based and is not definitive; you can always look at the slides a couple of days later to confirm or correct your reporting. While seeking a second opinion from a more knowledgeable collaborator or perhaps from a pathologist may be desired for unbiased evaluation, it is expected that such students should at least obtain basic information, such as cytoarchitectural consistency and morphological changes. These are usually sufficient in reporting microscopic findings. After all, whether for diagnosis or research, there would be a second opinion.

Conflict of interest: None

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15119858](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15119858)

AI declaration: Was used to correct grammatical errors in the English language.

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